

**Future scientific potential personnel in education
interdisciplinary integration and from dependence of use efficient
methods**

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In our republic Third Renaissance to the period foundation being created present in the circumstances education system quality in terms of national and foreign experience harmonized international to standards suitable way new to stage raise according to wide comprehensive reforms done increase for defined priority assignments done increase on the way the most important from tasks one continuously education system teaching in the process interdisciplinary integration to the road to put of possibilities efficient to use efficient organize of reaching modern technologies done is to increase . Especially our country the world to the community by joining managed to one at the time competitive personnel issue very important to the topic turning around has managed

Uzbek literary critic O. Sharafiddinov right as stated : " Infinite in the world big and small each one thing mutually in dependence created and one of another existence providing standing for the world to know organized pedagogical shape to be education in the process mother that's it unity , chambers relationship account taken it is necessary Other people in the psyche extortions understanding based on in students personality qualities to form directed literary interdisciplinary in education as well contact important importance occupation is enough Literature in teaching to efficiency reach for his at school teachable different study sciences with connection to provide separately attention focus necessary "

As you know , study sciences the amount Increase , of course , every always positive the result does not give . Because today's modern technology behind the hip to chase not but quality that there will be changes requirement is doing In this regard developed countries from experience use can Because they are already own education to the system integration take entered and integrative sciences current did Great Britain , Korea , Switzerland , Hungary , USA , Russia and others these are including Today's in the day our education integration into our system as well process come in came Integration means " whole " . the meaning means , so this thinking growth of the process different part and elements one to the whole is to combine . This is in education interdisciplinary relationship , sciences each other with closely depends without teaching shows .

Sciences integration by doing lesson when passed to the following attention to give need

- each one lesson certain to the goal directed to be need
- interdisciplinary to communications about selected additional material is passed topic with connection condition ;
- science students activity increase in order to they are with work ways determination can

Lesson only educational being without leaving , students humanity aspects to educate directed to be necessary Because speed century live we are our country on the world wide web from the news free that it is not each per second understood we will stay should , exactly today's in young people something source fast and it's easy analysis to do opportunity there is it is them something thing with surprise very difficult Subject from the content come came out without , nature , society , man thinking , development about knowledge our republic to the future trust and faith to form directed to be need And this student worldview expands . In general when integration lesson to each other suitable coming (topic in terms of) and thorough plan based on Created to be need

Primary stage to his teacher integrated to lessons transition easy because one himself everyone sciences teaches . A student how many young if so , that 's it less knows That's why for in the beginning integration possibilities limited . Primary in education in practice internal and interdisciplinary from connections use and development need Primary in education integration « little - little everyone from thing to » method have Children initial in education very a lot event , concept , sciences with get acquainted , but they are about elementary concept they get Next in years there is knowledge by filling and by expanding they go That's why for teacher one from diversity escape and colorful form and in methods lesson pass Demand will be done . Integrated lessons fatigue and tension from the students takes , of activity one from the type to the other pass at the expense of cleverness and to the present teaches . But in the early stages integrated to lessons so much don't give in recommendation will be done . Because of the child knowledge reserve a lot not , grammatical , mathematical and technical skills forming didn't have time . Because integration there is the subject expands , deep analysis to do Demand does , events summarizes their knowledge scope another sciences at the expense of expands . Students independent way that's all work to perform power not enough can Own in turn to the teacher very a lot requirements is placed . Integrated lesson from the teacher addition preparation , big knowledge , high occupation skills Demand does

Education process each one from the teacher big intelligence , patience , to students and own to the profession high affectionate to be Demand is enough

Teacher's always inquisitive , knowledge and experience increasing outgoing to be , students deep understand their internal the world notice get , grow and development degrees control by doing to go and necessary at the time help give get ability education and education of the process success provider are factors .

Summary by doing that's it we say maybe mathematics - physics and chemistry science the first to be poured and perfect is a step , and natural science is everything natural of sciences is a prelude - that is biology, chemistry , geography , physics , stories language is an ideal tool for learning because they are whole our life during us manages So , mathematics science all sciences is a prelude , exactly therefore for today in the day higher education institutions to study at the entrance all of directions access to the exam mathematics science mandatory block level entered , so it is the future generation each bilaterally mature capable by doing in education mathematics science since childhood to teach very important

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